

THE POSITIVE EFFECT OF LABORATORY ACTIVITIES ON THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN PHYSICS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ANNOTATION: *Opinions were expressed on the laws and regulations for the use of the Physics Room, laboratory rooms and pharmacy for reagents in secondary schools.*

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It is well known that the science of physics is one of the natural sciences, and it is the science that studies the way in which physical substances interact and change. Along with theoretical knowledge, the role of practical and laboratory work in the study of science is enormous. Practical work helps to further expand the imagination to supplement the theory. Laboratory work, practical work is carried out mainly in laboratories, especially in the Physics rooms of secondary schools.

In secondary schools, the Physics room will consist of a laboratory room and a pharmacy for reagents. The laboratory room will have cabinets for storing various instruments and reagents, desks for students to practice, various models and stands. Student desks and teacher-experienced desks are equipped according to the content of each lesson. There must be a faucet and a gas burner next to the table where the teacher demonstrates the experience.

Students use an alcohol lamp. The students will have a laboratory tripod, a test tube, a 100 or 250 ml tube, a 2 or 5 milliliter pipette, a 25 cm long glass rod, a beaker, a funnel and a porcelain glass. Solutions of different concentrations of salts, acids and bases are kept in the laboratory room (pharmacy) and, if necessary, poured into the laboratory by the laboratory assistant. In addition, the laboratory room should have a fire extinguisher (sandbox, fire extinguisher, etc.) and a first aid kit on one side and in a convenient place.

In any laboratory, of course, there is a specialist working as a laboratory assistant. Duties and responsibilities of each laboratory assistant are defined based on the specifics of the institution in which he works.

The laboratory assistant monitors the students' compliance with safety rules while performing laboratory work. The laboratory assistant must constantly improve his theoretical and practical knowledge and take an exam for the teacher every year. Every day at the end of the work, he checks that the electrical appliances in the cabinet are turned off, that there are no reagents left on the tables, that the taps and gas taps are closed, and then locks the cabinet. Every laboratory assistant should have a robe, goggles, rubber gloves. The laboratory assistant must always be neatly dressed, take care of himself, and wash his hands with soap after working with substances. It is not recommended to wear synthetic clothing in the laboratory.

The laboratory assistant and the teacher should work together to prepare for the training laboratory experiment, firstly, and secondly, without the participation of the student, that is, to conduct a specific experiment on a trial basis. Otherwise, the reliability of the experiment may be compromised if a significant part of the situation does not come out as desired (for example, if no gas escapes or the sediment does not fall or the color does not change) when showing the experiments to students.

The laboratory assistant prepares the necessary equipment and reagents for the experiment or laboratory training on the basis of a card drawn up by the teacher. In some cases, some necessary items may be forgotten by the laboratory assistant. For this reason, the teacher must review the prepared teaching aids and tell the laboratory assistant what is missing.

The use of active teaching methods in physics lessons, with a strong focus on the experiments and laboratory classes that form the basis of the lessons, to organize them correctly, to draw the students' full attention to the experiments that are performed, to ensure that students approach each event as a researcher.

The main purpose of the practical training is to find out how well the theoretical knowledge of all the topics covered has been mastered. All necessary equipment and reagents must be pre-installed during such training. Therefore, a few days before the training, the teacher writes in the laboratory assistant's work log, telling the laboratory assistant how to prepare.

Students' activities should be managed during the experiment, highlighting who is doing well, safety precautions, and monitoring outcomes.

At the end of the work it is necessary to leave a few minutes for pre-cleaning. When the work is completed, its results are discussed and recorded in a notebook.

After each laboratory work is completed, the teacher assigns a score to each student, taking into account the students' reports on the laboratory work and how they conducted the experiment.

In most cases, students do not pay good attention to the specific properties of the substances formed. Therefore, after evaluating the laboratory work, giving a brief explanation of the experiment performed will help you to master the lesson better.

The science of physics, and especially its laboratories, is not only interesting but also very responsible. It would be more appropriate for the teacher and the laboratory assistant to demonstrate the more complex laboratory work to the students first as a demonstration experiment, as well as to ensure that all students arrive on time for laboratory classes. is also very important.

If a student arrives late for class, he or she will not be able to understand the content of the experience, the sequence of events, and as a result will be left behind. It is best to start and end the experiment at the same time as possible. The procedure for performing the experiments should be strictly followed. It is advisable to set the time in advance. It is also advisable to follow the principle of simple - complex when performing experiments.

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